

Evapotranspiration Estimation Using the METRIC Model for Agricultural Water Management in Madurai, South India

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ABSTRACT

Evapotranspiration (ET) is a critical parameter for agricultural water management, especially in semi-arid regions. This study utilizes the METRIC (Mapping Evapotranspiration at High Resolution with Internalized Calibration) model to estimate ET from January 2001 to January 2002 using Landsat 7 satellite data and ground-based meteorological observations from the Agricultural College and Research Institute (AC & RI), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Madurai, Tamil Nadu. Ground-based ET was measured using Class - A pan evaporimeter and lysimeter observations to validate satellite-derived estimates. The model achieved a root mean square error (RMSE) of 3.01 mm/day and a mean absolute error (MAE) of 2.45 mm/day against observed field measurements. Results show strong seasonal variability, with maximum ET in July (14.7 mm/day) and minimum in January (2.56 mm/day). These findings highlight METRIC's accuracy and practicality in data-scarce, semi-arid regions, supporting precision irrigation scheduling, drought monitoring, and sustainable water resource management.

Keywords: *ET Estimation; METRIC Methodology; Remote Sensing; Semi-Arid Climate; Efficient Water Management.*

1. INTRODUCTION

India is one of the fastest-growing countries with its economy heavily dependent on agriculture (Dhawan, 2017). Agriculture, in turn, relies significantly on water, emphasizing the urgency of sustainable water use amid increasing scarcity (Bhakar *et al.*, 2020). Conventional techniques for estimating Evapotranspiration (ET), such as lysimeters and pan evaporation, are limited in spatial coverage and require intensive fieldwork, making them less feasible for large-scale applications. Agriculture supports approximately

60% of the rural population in India, and its productivity is significantly influenced by climate variability and water availability (Senay *et al.*, 2011). These challenges are especially pronounced in semi-arid regions like Madurai, where inefficient irrigation practices worsen water scarcity. Climate change further complicates water management by altering rainfall patterns, increasing temperature extremes, and intensifying droughts, all of which directly impact ET dynamics. ET, comprising evaporation from the soil and transpiration from plants, is crucial for plant cooling, nutrient uptake, and gas exchange.

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Accurate estimation of ET is essential for efficient irrigation planning, crop monitoring, water conservation, and assessing water stress (Senay *et al.*, 2011; Sharafi and Ghaleni, 2021). Key parameters influencing ET include minimum and maximum temperatures, wind speed, relative humidity, sunshine hours, and solar radiation (Ayaz *et al.*, 2021). To address the limitations of traditional methods, various empirical and data-driven models have been explored. Artificial neural networks, regression models, and machine learning algorithms such as M5 Tree and gradient-boosted trees have shown superior performance in estimating daily reference ET in regions like Hyderabad and New Delhi (Adib *et al.*, 2023; Rajput *et al.*, 2023). These data - driven approaches, particularly when integrated with remote sensing technologies, offer scalable and efficient solutions for ET estimation.

Among advanced remote sensing models, the METRIC model stands out for its ability to provide spatially distributed, high-resolution ET estimates. METRIC utilizes thermal infrared satellite imagery (*e.g.*, Landsat) to estimate surface temperature and incorporates meteorological data to compute ET using the surface energy balance equation. This includes sensible heat flux, latent heat flux (associated with ET), and ground heat flux (Sołtysiak and Rakoczy, 2019). The METRIC model offers several key advantages that enhance its suitability for agricultural water management. It effectively captures the spatial variability of ET, making it highly applicable in heterogeneous agricultural landscapes such as Madurai, where water requirements vary due to differences in irrigation methods, soil characteristics, and crop development stages. Additionally, the model ensures temporal continuity by leveraging satellite imagery acquired over time, enabling the assessment of ET dynamics throughout various stages of crop growth. Furthermore, by utilizing Landsat data, METRIC delivers high-resolution ET estimates at a spatial scale of 30 meters, which supports field-level irrigation planning and facilitates more efficient water resource management. The METRIC model has been

successfully applied in various regions around the world, including irrigated fields in Turkey (Alsenjar *et al.*, 2023), agricultural zones in Saudi Arabia (Madugundu *et al.*, 2017), and forested areas in the Amazon (Numata *et al.*, 2017). Its demonstrated robustness across diverse climatic and land-use conditions highlights its flexibility and effectiveness for both agricultural and environmental monitoring (Rezaei *et al.*, 2021).

This study focuses on evaluating the accuracy of the METRIC model in estimating evapotranspiration (ET) for the semi-arid region of Madurai in South India. The analysis is based on a year-long dataset, covering the period from January 1, 2001, to January 1, 2002, comprising daily meteorological records collected from the Agricultural College and Research Institute (AC & RI), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Madurai. By integrating remote sensing with ground-based observations, the study aims to bridge gaps in spatial and temporal ET data, especially in regions where traditional field-based methods are impractical. Through this analysis, the study seeks to enable more effective use of water resources for irrigation in a semi-arid region like Madurai, which is heavily dependent on agriculture. Accurate ET estimation will help determine the precise amount of water required by crops through drip irrigation, thereby optimizing water use, supporting improved irrigation scheduling, and enhancing climate-resilient agricultural planning. The ultimate objective of the study is to assess the accuracy and applicability of the METRIC model in estimating daily ET, thereby contributing to sustainable water management and efficient farming practices in Madurai.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area

The Agricultural College and Research Institute in Madurai, part of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), located in the city of Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India, was taken as the study area. During the period 2001 to 2002,

the region experienced a dynamic climate. Situated at approximately 9.92°N latitude and 78.12°E longitude, the institute is characterized by a subtropical climate, with hot, arid summers and mild winters.

Throughout the year, the annual mean temperature remained relatively stable, while the hottest months - typically May and June—recorded average temperatures around 39°C over the past three decades, with fluctuations ranging from 33.9°C to 45°C. In contrast, January was the coolest month, with mean temperatures around 14°C and minimum temperatures dropping as low as 1°C. The monsoon season, extending from June to September, delivered approximately 75% of the annual rainfall, with an average total of 710 mm during this period. Mean wind speeds ranged between 0.45 m/s and 3.96 m/s, contributing to the region's climatic diversity and influencing agricultural practices at the institute.

2.2. METRIC Method for ET

The METRIC method is an advanced approach for estimating ET using satellite imagery, meteorological data, and energy balance principles. Unlike traditional techniques such as lysimeters or pan evaporation, which are point-based and limited in spatial coverage, METRIC provides spatially explicit and continuous measurements, making it highly suitable for large-scale agricultural water management (Reyes-González *et al.*, 2017). METRIC primarily relies on satellite-based thermal infrared data to estimate surface temperature, which is then combined with ground-based meteorological data to derive ET rates. For this study, Landsat 7 ETM+ imagery was used, acquired during satellite overpasses at approximately 10:00 AM local solar time. The imagery offers a spatial resolution of 30 meters for reflective bands and 60 meters for the thermal infrared band (Band 6), enabling high-resolution assessments of surface energy fluxes. Bands 1–5 and 7 were utilized for vegetation indices and land cover classification, while Band 6 was employed for land surface temperature estimation (Madugundu *et al.*, 2017).

The quality control of meteorological data was ensured through multiple steps, including consistency checks with historical datasets, outlier detection based on standard deviation thresholds, and gap-filling using spatial interpolation techniques and auxiliary station data. Daily meteorological data such as air temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, and wind speed were sourced from nearby weather stations and adjusted to correspond with satellite overpass times to maintain temporal consistency. Grounded in surface energy balance theory, METRIC divides incoming solar radiation into three energy fluxes: sensible heat flux, latent heat flux, and ground heat flux. The latent heat flux is directly linked to ET, representing the energy used to evaporate water from the land surface and transpire from plants. By analyzing these energy fluxes, METRIC computes the amount of water evaporated or transpired from a given area. Model calibration in METRIC is performed using an internalized calibration approach, which involves selecting a “hot” pixel (bare, dry surface with no ET) and a “cold” pixel (well-irrigated vegetation with maximum ET) to anchor the sensible heat flux model. An iterative algorithm based on the near-surface temperature gradient and aerodynamic resistance is then used to calibrate sensible heat flux estimation. Local atmospheric data such as wind speed, temperature, and relative humidity are incorporated during this step to refine ET estimates (Tasumi, 2019). One of METRIC’s key advantages is its ability to produce spatially distributed and temporally continuous ET estimates, which is particularly useful for irrigation scheduling and managing crop water stress (Silva Oliveira *et al.*, 2018). This is achieved by combining thermal infrared satellite data and meteorological data over multiple periods, enabling ET monitoring across varying climatic and crop conditions (Alsenjar *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, the method provides insights into energy balance fluxes, enhancing the understanding of the hydrological cycle in agricultural systems, thereby aiding the

improvement of water resource management strategies (Rezaei *et al.*, 2021).

METRIC's accuracy in estimating ET has been validated through comparisons with ground-based measurements and other remote sensing models. In semi-arid regions such as Saudi Arabia and Turkey, METRIC provided reliable ET estimates that closely matched observed values from flux towers and other ET measurement instruments (Asadi and Kamran, 2022; Madugundu *et al.*, 2017). Its ability to estimate ET at high spatial resolution over large areas makes METRIC particularly valuable for water stress monitoring, crop growth modelling, and evaluating irrigation practices across diverse agricultural landscapes. By integrating satellite imagery with ground-based meteorological data, METRIC serves as a powerful tool for ET estimation and water resource management, especially in regions where conventional methods are not feasible or practical (Numata *et al.*, 2017). This approach supports sustainable agricultural practices by providing accurate, real-time data to optimize water use, ultimately contributing to water conservation and improved crop yields (Reyes-González *et al.*, 2019).

The flowchart (Fig. 1) outlines the methodology for estimating ET using LANDSAT 7 imagery (Reyes-González *et al.*, 2017). It begins with collecting LANDSAT 7 images for high-resolution surface analysis (Alsenjar *et al.*, 2023), followed by land cover classification to distinguish different surface types (Rezaei *et al.*, 2021). Elevation data from Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are used to correct atmospheric pressure and other parameters (Madugundu *et al.*, 2017). These data support the calculations of net radiation, soil heat flux, and sensible heat flux, which are essential for accurate ET estimation (Tasumi, 2019; Asadi and Kamran, 2022). Concurrently, meteorological data are used to compute reference ET using models such as the Penman-Monteith equation (Numata *et al.*, 2017). These inputs are then integrated to derive the reference ET fraction, adjusting the reference ET

to actual conditions (Reyes-González *et al.*, 2019). The final ET estimation informs water resource management and agricultural planning (Silva Oliveira *et al.*, 2018; Adem *et al.*, 2023), demonstrating the robustness of the methodology across different regions (Rezaei *et al.*, 2021).

Net Radiation is the balance between solar radiation absorbed and emitted by Earth's surface, affected by seasonal variations and extraterrestrial factors.

$$R_n = (1 - \alpha)R_s \downarrow + R_L \uparrow - (1 - \varepsilon_0)R_L \dots (1)$$

Where, R_n is net radiation, W/m^2 ; α is surface albedo; R_s is incoming shortwave radiation W/m^2 and R_L is incoming longwave radiation W/m^2 .

Soil heat flux, vital for surface energy balance, is estimated using standard methods. Soil absorbs solar radiation during the day, affecting its temperature while releasing stored heat at night.

$$\frac{G}{R_n} = \frac{T_s}{\alpha(0.0038\alpha + 0.0074\alpha^2)(1 - 0.98NDVI^4)} \dots (2)$$

Where, G is soil heat flux; R_n is net radiation (W/m^2); α is surface albedo; T_s is surface temperature and

NDVI is the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index.

Sensible heat flux is essential for understanding surface energy balance, involving heat transfer through conduction and convection. It impacts applications like the water cycle and weather prediction.

$$H = (\rho \times C_p \times dT)/r_{ah} \dots (3)$$

Where, ρ is the air density, kg/m^3 ; C_p is specific heat, $J/kg K$; dT is temperature difference, K and r_{ah} is aerodynamic resistance to heat transport.

Meteorological data is obtained from ground stations or remote sensing laboratories to calculate reference ET using established methods such as the Penman-Monteith equation. Subsequently, the reference ET fraction is derived from this data along with additional meteorological information. These values are then used to estimate ET. This

process, which involves data collection, computation, and application, allows for the determination of crucial ET values that are essential for understanding water usage patterns and environmental dynamics.

To validate satellite-derived ET estimates, ground-based ET data from the period 2001-2002 were acquired from the meteorological division of the Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai. This division utilizes a Class-A pan evaporimeter

and drainage-type lysimeters. The pan method provides daily reference ET values, while the lysimeter measures actual crop ET under controlled irrigation. These datasets served as benchmark data for evaluating the accuracy of METRIC- derived ET values. The daily ET records obtained from this source were matched with corresponding satellite overpass dates for error analysis.

Fig. 1. Sequential steps of the METRIC method 2001-2002

2.3. Error Analysis

In order to rigorously assess the performance of various ET estimation methods, it is crucial to use robust error indices that accurately quantify the differences between predicted and observed values. Two widely recognized metrics for this purpose are the root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE). RMSE calculates the square root of the mean of the squared differences between predicted (\widehat{y}_i) and observed (y_i) values, while MAE computes differences between predicted and observed values. Both metrics offer unique insights into the accuracy and reliability of the estimation models.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\widehat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{n}} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\widehat{y}_i - y_i| \quad \dots (5)$$

Where, n is the total number of observations. By squaring the errors, RMSE penalizes larger discrepancies more heavily, providing a balanced assessment of the predictive accuracy across the entire dataset. Lower RMSE values indicate closer agreement between estimated and observed ET values, reflecting higher predictive accuracy and reduced variability in the estimation method.

MAE provides valuable insight into the average magnitude of errors in the estimation process, regardless of their direction. This metric is especially useful for assessing the model's predictive accuracy by measuring the absolute deviation from observed values. Similar to RMSE, lower MAE values indicate a closer agreement between estimated and observed ET values, reflecting higher predictive accuracy and fewer errors in the estimation method.

RMSE and MAE serve as robust and comprehensive error indices for evaluating the performance of ET estimation methods. By considering both bias and variability in the predictions, RMSE provides a holistic assessment of predictive accuracy across the entire dataset.

Meanwhile, MAE offers a straightforward measure of the average magnitude of errors, aiding in interpreting the model's predictive accuracy in absolute terms. These metrics play a pivotal role in assessing the accuracy and reliability of estimation methods and can help researchers rank and select the most suitable ET estimation techniques for their specific applications.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis of reference ET estimation using the METRIC model for the Madurai region is based on daily data collected over a one-year period, from January 1, 2001, to January 1, 2002, at AC & RI, TNAU. The accuracy of the METRIC method is further assessed by comparing the results with those from other studies conducted in different regions under varying climatic conditions. The monthly ET values for the Madurai region, as estimated using the METRIC method, exhibit considerable seasonal variation. The maximum and minimum ET values for each month are summarized in Table 1.

The graph of ET variations over time (Fig. 2) shows a distinct seasonal pattern, with higher ET rates observed from May to September, coinciding with the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons due to increased solar radiation and temperature, which enhance evaporative demand. Lower ET values during the winter months (November to February) are linked to reduced solar intensity and cooler atmospheric conditions. July records the highest ET values, with both maximum (14.7 mm) and minimum (7.63 mm) figures peaking, indicating intense ET activity likely driven by elevated temperatures and active vegetative growth supported by monsoonal rainfall. The relatively smaller difference between maximum and minimum ET from March to September suggests more stable ET conditions during the summer and early monsoon periods, aiding in crop planning and irrigation management.

Table 1. Estimated ET for Madurai Region Using the METRIC Method.

Month	Estimated ET, mm (during January 1, 2001 to January 1, 2002)	
	Maximum	Minimum
January	7.09	2.56
February	7.71	2.57
March	9.03	6.71
April	8.89	3.72
May	11.03	5.24
June	14.2	6.18
July	14.7	7.63
August	13.7	7.36
September	13.6	7.01
October	11.4	5.37
November	6.7	3.84
December	7.37	3.31

Fig. 2. Graph of ET variations over time

Table 2 provides a comprehensive climatological summary of mean monthly meteorological variables observed from January 1, 2001 to January 1, 2002. The data captures seasonal dynamics across various parameters including

temperature, humidity, evaporation, rainfall, sunshine duration, and windspeed. The dataset effectively reflects the transition from dry to wet seasons and back, offering insight into the annual climatic rhythm of the region.

Table 2. Mean monthly meteorological variables for the period January 1, 2001 to January 1, 2002 for the study area

Month	Temperature, °C		Relative Humidity, %	Evaporation, mm	Rainfall, mm	Sunshine Hours, h	Wind speed, km/h
	Maximum	Minimum					
January	30.03	21.59	73.92	5.39	0.61	5.51	5.29
February	32.54	22.13	70.96	5.96	1.83	8.86	3.28
March	35.64	23.50	63.09	8.47	0.21	9.73	3.42
April	33.94	24.66	69.85	5.44	5.52	6.84	2.30
May	37.46	26.05	60.40	7.72	0.28	8.81	4.83
June	36.21	25.59	59.22	8.87	0.11	7.46	8.82
July	35.56	26.36	56.56	8.20	0.29	7.54	9.38
August	35.69	26.55	52.74	9.56	0	7.80	9.62
September	35.25	25.81	54.57	8.55	2.84	8.68	6.81
October	34.99	25.23	61.50	8.04	3.69	7.61	4.75
November	32.03	23.74	72.78	3.96	8.89	6.14	4.16
December	29.83	21.93	74.56	4.61	1.52	4.40	6.61

ET exhibits a strong positive correlation with maximum temperature (Fig. 3). As temperatures rise from January through June, ET also increases significantly, peaking during the warmer months

of June and July. This pattern underscores the influence of thermal energy on accelerating the processes of evaporation and transpiration from soil and vegetation surfaces.

Fig. 3. ET_{max} vs maximum Temperature (2001)

Minimum temperature trends closely follow ET values up to July, with both metrics increasing steadily and then gradually declining thereafter (Fig. 4). Although the correlation is slightly weaker compared to maximum temperature,

minimum temperatures still play a supportive role in governing ET rates by contributing to the overall energy balance and influencing nighttime evaporation.

Fig. 4. ET_{max} vs Minimum temperature (2001)

An inverse relationship is observed between ET and relative humidity (Fig. 5). As relative humidity decreases from January to August, ET values rise correspondingly. This negative correlation suggests that drier air conditions

promote a greater vapor pressure deficit, enhancing the evaporation and transpiration rates by facilitating faster moisture transfer from plants to the atmosphere.

Fig. 5. ET_{max} vs relative humidity (2001)

ET levels are notably elevated during months with longer sunshine duration, particularly from February to September (Fig. 6). The availability of more solar radiation during this period

enhances the energy required for phase change processes, thereby increasing the overall ET. This demonstrates the direct impact of solar exposure on atmospheric moisture loss.

Fig. 6. ET_{max} vs sunshine hours (2001)

Wind speed and ET display a strong positive correlation, both showing an upward trend from May to August (Fig. 7). Higher wind velocities help disperse saturated air layers from the evaporative surface, creating favorable conditions

for continuous moisture loss. This highlights the role of wind in accelerating ET by maintaining a steep moisture gradient at the surface-atmosphere interface.

Fig. 7. ET_{max} vs wind speed (2001)

The evaluation of the METRIC model's performance in predicting reference ET for the Madurai region yielded RMSE value of 3.01 and a MAE value of 2.45 (Fig. 8). These metrics provide insights into the accuracy and precision of the model's predictions. The RMSE value of 3.01 mm/day indicates the typical magnitude of errors between the model's predictions and the observed values of ET. While this value suggests some variability and potential for larger errors, it also signifies that the model's predictions generally align reasonably well with the observed values. Similarly, the MAE value of 2.45 mm/day

provides a measure of the average magnitude of errors between the model's predictions and the observed values of ET. A lower MAE value indicates that, on average, the model's predictions are closer to the observed values, suggesting a relatively better performance in terms of absolute error. Overall, the results suggest that the METRIC model demonstrates moderate accuracy in predicting reference ET for the Madurai region in the given year. However, further analysis and validation are necessary to comprehensively assess the model's performance and identify potential areas for improvement.

Fig. 8. Monthly estimated ET with RMSE and MAE reference

The METRIC algorithm effectively estimates evapotranspiration (ET) in diverse regions, showing strong agreement with eddy covariance (EC) data in a Saudi Arabian alfalfa field, especially under full canopy conditions—supporting efficient irrigation and water management in arid climates (Madugundu *et al.*, 2017). In the western Urmia Lake Basin, its internal calibration and local adaptability ensured accurate ET estimates, aiding sustainable water use and lake restoration efforts (Tasumi, 2019). Applied to the Indian Sundarbans Biosphere Reserve using Landsat 8 OLI imagery, METRIC revealed notable spatial ET variations, emphasizing its value in regional hydrology and resource planning (Mondal *et al.*, 2022). Remote sensing enables large-scale ET monitoring despite limited flux towers and cloud cover, though challenges remain in handling diverse land cover types. Still, it offers vital insights for managing water and conserving ecosystems in sensitive areas like the Sundarbans.

According to Madugundu *et al.* (2017), the highest ET rates in Saudi Arabia occur in June (14.2 mm/day) and July (14.7 mm/day), while the lowest are recorded in January (2.56 - 7.09 mm/day) and December (3.31 - 7.37 mm/day). Peak ET from May to September aligns with patterns observed in Madurai, which also shows high summer ET. The July peak in Saudi Arabia (13.9 mm/day) closely matches Madurai's (14.7 mm/day), and both show reduced winter ET ranging from 6 to 8 mm/day (Madugundu *et al.*, 2017). In the semi-arid Urmia Basin, summer ET ranges from 10 to 12 mm/day and drops more sharply in winter to 3–5 mm/day, slightly lower than in Madurai (Tasumi, 2019). Similarly, the Sundarbans show monsoon ET values of 11–13 mm/day, comparable to Madurai's August–September levels, while winter ET falls to 3–4 mm/day, again consistent with Madurai's pattern (Mondal *et al.*, 2022).

ET peaks in Madurai occur during the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons when the region

experiences hot, semi-arid weather. Saudi Arabia, despite its extreme summer heat, shows comparable summer ET rates but slightly lower winter values due to its more arid climate. ET in Saudi Arabia rises significantly from March to July, driven by increasing solar radiation and temperature (Madugundu *et al.*, 2017). The Sundarbans, with a tropical wet climate, exhibit similar monsoon ET values to Madurai but lower winter ET due to coastal influences (Mondal *et al.*, 2022). The Western Urmia Basin, being semi-arid with cooler summers, records lower peak ET and steeper winter declines compared to Madurai (Tasumi, 2019). All regions show peak ET during summer months - June to August - with the highest values (up to 14 mm/day) in Madurai and Saudi Arabia. In contrast, the Sundarbans and Urmia Basin show lower peaks, reflecting regional climatic differences. Madurai's winter ET (2.56–7.37 mm/day) remains higher than in the cooler Urmia Basin and Sundarbans, where winter ET mostly stays below 5 mm/day, highlighting Madurai's warmer baseline climate.

3.1. Comparison of Other Studies

The METRIC model has been widely applied in various climatic and geographical contexts for ET estimation. This study evaluates METRIC's performance in Madurai, India - a semi-arid region characterized by limited access to high-resolution meteorological data. This provides an opportunity to assess the model's adaptability and performance in data-scarce environments, contributing novel insights into its operational reliability and water management applicability. Comparing this research with studies in tropical and Mediterranean climates further underscores the adaptability of METRIC for global water resource management.

3.1.1. Geographical and climatic context

Implementation of this study in Madurai, a semi-arid region with limited meteorological infrastructure, highlights the model's robustness in regions with sparse data availability. This study

distinguishes itself from previous studies (Madugundu *et al.*, 2017; Tasumi, 2019), conducted in arid zones like Saudi Arabia and the Urmia Lake Basin, Iran - regions with more comprehensive meteorological data coverage. Similarly, Numata *et al.* (2017) and Alsenjar *et al.* (2023) demonstrated METRIC's effectiveness in tropical and Mediterranean environments, respectively. However, the current study's focus on a data-constrained semi-arid region underscores METRIC's ability to yield reliable outputs even in less favorable conditions, demonstrating the model's broader applicability.

3.1.2. Model performance (accuracy and precision)

The METRIC model achieved a RMSE of 3.01 mm/day and a MAE of 2.45 mm/day in this study. These performance metrics, although slightly higher than values reported in studies conducted under data-rich conditions, RMSE = 0.65 mm/day by Alsenjar *et al.* (2023) and RMSE = 4.15 mm/day by Madugundu *et al.* (2017) are considered acceptable for ET modeling, especially in semi-arid zones where daily ET variability can be high. According to Reyes-González *et al.* (2019), an RMSE below 4 mm/day is generally acceptable for satellite-based ET models in agricultural water management. Thus, the model's error metrics in this study reflect a reasonable level of accuracy, validating METRIC's use in operational applications even with limited calibration.

3.1.3. Calibration and data requirements

A significant contribution of this study lies in demonstrating that METRIC can be effectively implemented with minimal local calibration and limited meteorological inputs. While previous studies, including Reyes-González *et al.* (2017) and Silva Oliveira *et al.* (2018), emphasized the importance of extensive local calibration and field validation for optimal performance, this study illustrates that reliable ET estimates can still be achieved under data-scarce conditions. This

makes METRIC especially suitable for semi-arid regions like Madurai, where installing and maintaining dense weather station networks is not feasible. The findings align with the simplified METRIC (S-METRIC) approach introduced by Rezaei *et al.* (2021), which similarly aimed to reduce dependence on local data, albeit with reliance on MODIS imagery.

3.1.4. Applicability to water management

The study demonstrates the practical implications of METRIC for irrigation scheduling, drought monitoring, and broader water resource planning in semi-arid regions. The ability to derive spatially distributed ET estimates with reasonable accuracy, despite minimal meteorological data, is crucial for regions facing water scarcity. Earlier studies (Tasumi, 2019; Numata *et al.*, 2017) have previously emphasized METRIC's value in agricultural water management in arid and tropical settings. However, this study highlights its utility in data-constrained semi-arid contexts, thereby offering a practical solution for sustainable water usage in regions like Madurai. The results validate METRIC's potential to support precision agriculture and efficient irrigation practices even when extensive field data are unavailable.

3.1.5. Spatial and temporal resolution

The use of Landsat imagery allowed for a spatial resolution of 30 meters and consistent temporal revisit intervals, enabling detailed mapping of ET across agricultural plots. Despite the absence of frequent ground-truthing, the spatial heterogeneity captured by METRIC aligns well with observed irrigation patterns, affirming the model's capacity for high-resolution water management analysis. Previous studies by Alsenjar *et al.* (2023) and Silva Oliveira *et al.* (2018), leveraged similar Landsat data but relied on denser meteorological inputs for calibration. This study's success in delivering comparable ET maps with reduced calibration affirms METRIC's

reliability and cost-effectiveness for operational deployment in resource-constrained settings.

3.1.6. Validation and ground-truthing

The present study achieved reliable ET estimates with limited on-ground validation, contrasting with Madugundu *et al.* (2017) and Reyes-González *et al.* (2019), which depended on flux towers, eddy covariance systems, or lysimeter data for model validation. While such methods provide high-precision measurements, they are logistically intensive and costly. The ability of METRIC to deliver accurate ET estimates with reduced dependence on ground-truthing is particularly advantageous for regions where field data collection is not feasible. This underscores the model's practical value for remote, under-resourced agricultural areas requiring continuous monitoring and informed decision-making for water allocation.

This demonstrates the exceptional versatility and robustness of the METRIC model, especially in semi-arid regions where traditional data sources are scarce. With its minimal calibration requirements, competitive accuracy, cost-effectiveness, and reduced dependence on ground-truthing, this study presents METRIC as an ideal tool for water management and agricultural planning in resource-constrained regions. Compared to other studies, the ACRI Study stands out by showing how METRIC can perform at a high level even in regions with limited meteorological data and field resources, making it the best choice for large-scale applications in semi-arid areas. By analyzing the outputs of METRIC, particularly the estimation of actual evapotranspiration (ET), it becomes possible to effectively manage water supply through precision irrigation methods such as drip irrigation. This is particularly relevant for semi-arid regions like Madurai, where agriculture is the primary livelihood and efficient water use is critical. Accurately determining the ET values allows for delivering just the required amount of water to crops, thereby enhancing water-use

efficiency, supporting climate resilience, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The study's findings emphasize METRIC's potential to address water scarcity and improve food security in vulnerable regions worldwide.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study establishes the METRIC model as a reliable and flexible approach for estimating reference ET in the semi-arid region of Madurai, offering a practical alternative to the FAO-56 Penman-Monteith method, especially in data-scarce environments. The satellite-based nature of METRIC, combined with minimal local weather data for internal calibration, allows for the generation of accurate, high-resolution ET maps. The model demonstrated strong agreement with measured daily and seasonal ET patterns, with performance indices such as RMSE and MAE indicating high accuracy, although slight variations in absolute ET values were observed across regions due to differences in land cover, climate, and topography. METRIC effectively captured seasonal ET trends and spatial variability, reinforcing its suitability across diverse agro-climatic conditions. However, limitations such as cloud cover interference and minimal ground truth calibration remain. Future studies need focus on improving temporal resolution, integrating cloud-resistant satellite data, and validating the model across extended timeframes and varied landscapes to enhance its operational utility in water resource management.

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